

Measurement Guidelines for aerosol high-power lidars

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Applicability of the document

These guidelines apply to the ACTRIS National Facilities operating aerosol high-power lidars and to the EARLINET-ACTRIS associated lidar stations.

Acronyms

- ACTRIS - Aerosol, Clouds and Trace gases Research InfraStructure
- ACTRIS GA – ACTRIS General Assembly
- ARES – Aerosol Remote Sensing unit of the ACTRIS Data Centre
- ARS – Aerosol Remote Sensing
- CARPORT – CARS workflow management portal
- CARS - Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing
- CLU – Cloud Remote Sensing unit of the ACTRIS Data Centre
- CCRES - Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing
- DC – Data Centre
- MP – Mobile Platform
- NF - National Facility
- NRT – Near-real time (less than 3 days from the measurements)
- OP – Observational Platform
- PI – Principal Investigator
- RI Comm – Research Infrastructure Committee
- RRT – Real-real time (less than 3 hours form the measurement)
- SCC – Single Calculus Chain

Reference documents

- [1]. [Documentation on technical concepts and requirements for ACTRIS Observational Platforms](#)
- [2]. [ACTRIS NF Labelling Plan](#)
- [3]. [Descriptions of the workflows between ACTRIS components](#)
- [4]. [ACTRIS Data Management Plan](#)
- [5]. [CARS implementation plan](#)
- [6]. [ACTRIS vocabulary](#)
- [7]. ACTRIS principles for evaluating data provision, service provision and QA/QC
- [8]. Labelling of the ACTRIS National Facilities operating Aerosol Remote Sensing instruments
- [9]. Guidelines for EARLINET-ACTRIS associated stations to access QA services
- [10]. Technical requirements for ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms
- [11]. Technical requirements for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating aerosol high-power lidars
- [12]. Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
- [13]. Quality Assurance Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars

1 Introduction

Aerosol remote sensing instruments as considered by ACTRIS are:

- a) aerosol high-power lidars;
- b) automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers;
- c) automatic low-power lidars and ceilometers.

Aerosol high-power lidars are operated by ACTRIS National Facilities either as part of the Observational Platforms (at fixed site, in synergy with collocated automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers), or onboard Mobile Platforms (movable, potentially with other instruments).

Measurement guidelines in this document apply specifically to aerosol high-power lidars, operated by Observational Platforms and by Mobile Platforms.

In order to be labelled as **ACTRIS National Facility**, both the Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms, and the Mobile Platforms operating aerosol remote sensing instruments must undergo the labelling process. The labelling process is described in [Labelling of the ACTRIS National Facilities operating Aerosol Remote Sensing instruments](#).

Aerosol high-power lidars can also be operated by other lidar stations or lidar networks, e.g. EARLINET. Although not all of the EARLINET stations are officially part of ACTRIS, they can benefit from CARS and ARES support if they are providing data to the ACTRIS Data Centre and follow the protocols issued by CARS and ARES. In the following, these lidar stations will be referred as "EARLINET-ACTRIS associated lidar station".

Measurement guidelines in this document apply also to EARLINET-ACTRIS associated lidar station.

In order to be accepted as **EARLINET-ACTRIS associated station**, and to receive support from CARS and ARES, the EARLINET stations must undergo the technical acceptance process. The acceptance process is described in [Guidelines for EARLINET-ACTRIS associated stations to access QA services](#).

Depending on the type of the facility and of the degree of fulfilment of the technical requirements, ACTRIS data products are ([ACTRIS vocabulary](#)):

- **ACTRIS labelled:** Data are collected in accordance with ACTRIS procedures, observation is conducted at an ACTRIS National Facility.
- **ACTRIS compliant:** Data are collected in accordance with ACTRIS procedures and comply with the requirements for this variable. The facility component has not necessarily undergone the full ACTRIS labelling process nor is necessarily conducted at an ACTRIS National Facility.
- **ACTRIS associated:** Data partly complying with ACTRIS requirements after start of ACTRIS-ERIC

Depending on the level of quality assurance, ACTRIS data products are ([ACTRIS Data Management Plan](#)):

- **Level 0 data:** Raw sensor output. Native resolution, metadata necessary for next level.
- **Level 1 data:** Calibrated and quality assured data with minimum level of quality control.
- **Level 2 data:** Approved and fully quality controlled ACTRIS data product or geophysical variable.
- **Level 3 data:** Elaborated ACTRIS data products derived by post-processing of ACTRIS Level 0 - 1 -2 data, and data from other sources. The data can be gridded or not

This document describes the guidelines for the aerosol high-power lidar data flow, to be implemented by the ACTRIS National Facilities operating aerosol high-power lidars (Observational Platforms and Mobile Platforms), and by the ACTRIS associated lidar stations.

- General considerations are presented in [Section 2](#).
- The measurements schedule for the aerosol high-power lidars is described in [Section 3](#).
- The step-by-step workflow for the provision of data to the ACTRIS Data Centre is described in [Section 4](#).
- The list of ACTRIS aerosol remote sensing variables is provided in [Annex 1](#).
- Schematics of the workflow for the ACTRIS aerosol remote sensing measurements (lidar and photometer) is described in [Annex 2](#).
- The list of input parameters for the SCC operational configurations is provided in [Annex 3](#).

2 General considerations

2.1 Principles applicable to data production

Principle 1: Data products calculated from aerosol high-power lidar measurements are considered "ACTRIS data" only if they are originating from an ACTRIS National Facility or an ACTRIS-associated EARLINET station, and are centrally processed at the ACTRIS DC.

Principle 2: ACTRIS National Facilities operating aerosol high-power lidars and the EARLINET-ACTRIS associated lidar station must provide **operational data products** to the ACTRIS Data Centre, setting up an valid operational configuration in the Single Calculus Chain (SCC).

Principle 3: ACTRIS National Facilities operating aerosol high-power lidars and EARLINET-ACTRIS associated lidar station can also setup and use Single Calculus Chain (SCC) experimental configurations for their own experiments and specific needs. Data products calculated with SCC experimental configurations will not be considered as fully quality controlled.

Principle 4: ACTRIS Level 2 and Level 3 data products can only be produced if the data is processed with a **valid SCC operational configuration**, i.e. an SCC operational configuration within its approved validity period.

Principle 5: ACTRIS data products produced with an SCC operational configuration outside its approved validity period, as well as data products calculated by using SCC experimental configurations are ACTRIS Level 1 data.

2.2 ACTRIS data types

Data provided to the ACTRIS Data Centre by the **ACTRIS National Facilities** are tagged as:

- "**ACTRIS compliant data**" if all technical requirements are met, the associated SOPs and QAPs issued by CARS and ARES are followed, and the data is submitted to the ACTRIS Data Centre according to the measurement guidelines ([Section 3.1](#) for Observational Platforms / [Section 3.2](#) for Mobile Platforms);
- "**ACTRIS labelled data**" as soon as the ACTRIS label is granted (according to [ACTRIS principles for evaluating data provision, service provision and QA/QC](#)
- Labelling of the ACTRIS National Facilities operating Aerosol Remote Sensing instruments).

Data provided to the ACTRIS Data Centre by the **EARLINET-ACTRIS associated lidar station** are tagged as:

- "**ACTRIS associated data**" if not all the technical requirements are met but the associated SOPs and QAPs issued by CARS and ARES are followed, and the data is submitted to the ACTRIS Data Centre according to the measurement guidelines ([Section 3.3](#));
- "**ACTRIS compliant data**" if all technical requirements are met, and the associated SOPs and QAPs issued by CARS are followed, and the data is submitted to the ACTRIS Data Centre according to the measurement guidelines ([Section 3.3](#));

2.3 Requirements for the provision of aerosol high-power lidar compliant/labelled data to the ACTRIS Data Centre

In order to provide ACTRIS compliant or labelled data (as applicable), the ACTRIS National Facilities operating aerosol high-power lidars and the EARLINET-ACTRIS associated lidar station must:

- Undergo the labelling (*Labelling of the ACTRIS National Facilities operating Aerosol Remote Sensing instruments*) or the acceptance process (*Guidelines for EARLINET-ACTRIS associated stations to access QA services*), as applicable;
- Fulfill the technical requirements for the aerosol high-power lidar (*Technical requirements for ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms* or *Technical requirements for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating aerosol high-power lidars*, as applicable)
- Apply the operation procedures for the aerosol high-power lidar (*Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars*)
- Apply the quality assurance procedures for the aerosol high-power lidar and tools (*Quality Assurance Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars*)
- Implement the general principles for data provision (*Section 2.1 of this document*)
- Follow the measurement schedule (*Section 3 of this document*)
- Implement and follow the workflow for the data provision to the ACTRIS Data Centre (*Section 4 of this document*)

2.4 Other considerations

The ACTRIS National Facilities operating aerosol high-power lidars and the EARLINET-ACTRIS associated lidar station have the responsibility to securely and permanently store and archive native data from the instruments and Level 0 data (raw data in the format to be submitted to the DC unit). In order to guarantee secure store and archive of such data, the National Facilities should organize their archive in two different physical locations.

ACTRIS operational data is produced with SCC operational configurations, following the operational workflow described in [Section 4](#) and [Annex 2](#) of this document. The SCC operational configurations are proposed by the Principle Investigator and checked by CARS and ARES.

ACTRIS National Facilities operating aerosol high-power lidars and the EARLINET-ACTRIS associated lidar station are responsible for reporting and updating the technical information about the instrument, and setting the appropriate SCC operational configurations to process the data. The list of parameters to be included in the SCC operational configurations is available in [Annex 3](#).

The validity period of the SCC operational configurations is proposed by CARS based on the QA activities, is approved by the Principal Investigator, and is implemented in the SCC database by ARES. A valid SCC operational configuration is locked for inhibiting editing. At the request of CARS, ARES can extend the validity of an SCC operational configuration.

3 Measurement schedule

3.1 Measurement schedule for the ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms

ACTRIS high-power aerosol lidars should be preferably operated continuously, in the absence of precipitation, fog or very low clouds. If the instrument is not automated, it must at least provide unbiased long-term regular observations following the **pre-defined schedule with 5 observations per week, each with a duration of minimum 3 hours:**

Tab. 1 Minimum schedule of measurements to be performed, weather permitting:

No.	Day of the week	Time of the day
1.	Monday	11:30 - 14:30 LT
2.	Monday	18:30 - 23:30 UT
3.	Wednesday	11:30 - 14:30 LT
4.	Thursday	18:30 - 23:30 UT
5.	Friday	18:30 - 23:30 UT

In order to allow comprehensive climatology, Saturday daytime measurements are recommended but not mandatory.

Furthermore, measurements are to be performed upon alert, e.g., in hazardous situations such as volcanic eruptions, for special events such as dust outbreaks or forest fires, and for dedicated satellite validation purposes. Satellite validation measurements will follow a specific strategy. Alerts and measurement schedules for collocated observations during satellite overpasses will be distributed by the ARES unit of the ACTRIS Data Centre.

Denser measurements schedule and continuous measurements are advisable for having a better understanding of the aerosol 4d fields and properties.

3.2 Measurement schedule for the ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Mobile Platforms

The schedule in case of Mobile platforms is defined by the user according to the objectives of the campaign / experiment.

Although not mandatory, it is advisable that, while not involved in a campaign or specific experiment, the lidars onboard of Mobile Platforms follow the measurement schedule of the ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms ([Section 3.1](#)).

3.3 Measurement schedule for the EARLINET-ACTRIS associated lidar station

In order to allow comprehensive climatology, EARLINET-ACTRIS associated lidar station must follow the schedule for the ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms ([Section 3.1](#)).

4 Step-by-step workflow for provision of aerosol high-power data to the ACTRIS Data Centre

The schematics of the workflow for provision of aerosol high-power data to the ACTRIS Data Centre is presented in [Annex 2](#).

4.1 Steps for setting up a valid operational configuration

In order to setup a valid operational configuration, the station must follow the following steps:

Preliminary steps (initial acceptance)

1. **Contact CARS** (carport@inoe.ro) to obtain an account for accessing the CARPORT platform
2. **Contact ARES** (earlinetdb@actris.ima.cnr.it) to obtain a station ID (3-letters code of the station, unique), and an account for accessing the Single Calculus Chain
3. **Register the lidar in CARPORT** (<https://carport.inoe.ro/>) – CARS will initially evaluate the instrument, and will accept the support provision
4. **Register the lidar to the Single Calculus Chain** (<https://scc.ima.cnr.it>). The instrument will be associated to a Lidar ID (for the internal use during data processing) and a lidar PID (for the public landing page)
5. **Fill in the instruments settings** in the SCC database – telescopes, lasers, channels - and the data products to be calculated. All the information provided is automatically accessible through the Handbook of Instruments (HoI).

Regular workflow (performance evaluation)

6. **Setup SCC lidar configurations** (as many combinations of channels and products as needed) in the SCC database – to each configuration will be assigned a configuration ID
7. **Introduce in CARPORT** the station ID and the lidar ID provided by the SCC
8. **Select the SCC configurations to be used in an operational way** (1 daytime + 1 nighttime, or 1 all day)
9. **Perform the QA tests** for the SCC configurations selected as candidates for the operations, and submit them to CARS (also via CARPORT), as scheduled
10. **Read and approve the QA report** in CARPORT
 - a. The QA report may contain different values for the instrument parameters than initially set; the PI must approve the new values
 - b. The QA report will contain CARS' recommendation for the start date of validity and end date of validity for each of the SCC operational configurations; the PI must approve the validity periods.

Following the approval of the QA report (including the validity period for each operational configuration), CARS will inform ARES, which will check the retrieval parameters (like assumed lidar ratio and angstrom) and if everything is fine will lock the SCC operational configurations.

4.2 Life cycle of the SCC operational configurations

SCC operational configuration has a standard validity period of 1 year.

The SCC operational configurations are valid until one of the following situations appears:

A. The validity period ends

CARS will schedule the lidar station for re-submission of QA tests at least one month before the validity end of the operational configurations. CARS will inform ARES about the re-submission of QA test. At that time, ARES suspends the validity of the SCC configuration: from that date the Level 2 data production is stopped. The lidar station must perform and submit new QA tests to CARS, via CARPORT. **Steps 9-10 are re-iterated.** Depending on the QA test results, one of the following applies:

- a. In case the performances of the instrument are the same as the ones obtained at previous QA tests, **the validity of the existing (locked) SCC operational configurations will be extended by ARES at the request of CARS.** Since that moment the Level 2 data production is re-activated with the same SCC operational configuration IDs. The preliminary QA report will be updated with the new validity end. The final QA report will be sent to the Principal Investigator.
- b. In case the performances of the instrument are different than the ones obtained at previous QA tests, **new SCC operational configurations will be implemented by ARES at the request of CARS.** The preliminary QA report will be updated with the new SCC operational configuration IDs and the corresponding validity periods. The final QA report will be sent to the Principal Investigator. Since the moment the new configuration is approved as operational configuration, the Level 2 data production is re-activated with the new SCC operational configuration IDs.

Note: If the station does not submit new QA tests, the validity will not be extended. Level 2 data will be produced up to the end of the validity, then will stop. In order to re-start the production of Level 2 data, the station must submit new QA tests, steps 9-10 are re-iterated and new valid operational configurations are in place.

B. The instrument is changing its status, location or performances

In case the lidar is moved, under repair or major upgrade/revision, or its performances are changed (e.g. a monthly check fails) **the station must immediately inform CARS about the issue.** If is the case, CARS informs ARES to end the validity and stop level 2 data production.

As soon as the situation is solved and stable, the Principal Investigator must inform CARS to schedule new QA tests. The lidar station must perform and submit new QA tests to CARS, via CARPORT. Steps 9-10 are re-iterated. New SCC operational configurations will be setup by ARES at the request of CARS. The final QA report will be sent to the Principal Investigator, including the new SCC operational configurations IDs and the corresponding validity periods. Since the moment the new configuration is approved as operational configuration, the Level 2 data production is re-activated with the new SCC operational configuration IDs.

4.3 Life cycle of the Level 2 data production

Only measurements processed with an SCC operational configuration and collected during its validity period will enable the Level 2 data production. It is the responsibility of the lidar station to request the suspension of the validity period (and therefore the production of Level 2 data):

- One month before the end of the validity of the existing operational configurations, or
- In case the instrument changes its status:
 - The lidar is moved to another location, or
 - The lidar undergoes upgrades, major maintenance or repairs, or
 - The lidar changes the performances

In order to stop the validity period (and therefore the production of Level 2 data), the NF must promptly and efficiently inform CARS and ARES of this need reporting also the related motivations through CARPORT. Direct emails are to be avoided.

Measurements collected during the periods of operational configuration suspension are provided as Level 1 data.

Once the final QA report is issued by CARS, the data related to the suspension period can be re-processed by the station and submitted to the ACTRIS Data Centre.

- a. **In case the validity was extended** by ARES at the request of CARS, the PI must re-process data with the **same SCC operational configuration ID** as before, starting with the date when the Level 2 data production was stopped and then request the upload of Level 2 data to the ACTRIS Data Centre
- b. **In case a new SCC operational configuration was set** by ARES at the request of CARS, the PI must re-process data with the **new SCC operational configuration ID**, starting with the date of the start validity of the new SCC operational configuration. Then the NF should request the upload of the data to the ACTRIS Data Centre

For the regular process described in [Section 4.2](#), point A, there will be no gap in the Level 2 data. Either the re-processing is done with the same SCC operational configurations (having extended validity), or the re-processing is done with new SCC operational configurations (having a start validity at the time of the QA tests).

In all other situations, gaps in Level 2 will occur.

Note: It is the responsibility of the lidar station to use the valid SCC operational configurations for the right time period when re-processing the measurements.

Annex 1. List of aerosol remote sensing variables

Variable	Data product level	Requirement	Aerosol high-power lidar	Sun/sky/lunar photometer
Attenuated backscatter profile	L1, L2	Minimum		
Volume depolarization profile	L1, L2	Minimum		
Particle backscatter coefficient profile	L1, L2	Minimum		
Particle extinction coefficient profile	L1, L2	Minimum		
Lidar ratio profile	L1, L2	Minimum		
Ångström exponent profile	L1, L2	Optimum		
Backscatter-related Ångström exponent profile	L1, L2	Optimum		
Particle depolarization ratio profile	L1, L2	Minimum		
Particle layer geometrical properties (height and thickness)	L1, L2	Minimum		
Particle layer optical properties (extinction, backscatter, lidar ratio, Ångström exponent, depolarization ratio, optical depth)	L1, L2	Minimum		
Column integrated extinction	L1, L2	Minimum		
Spectral Downward Sky Radiances	L1	Minimum		
Direct Sun/Moon Extinction Aerosol Optical Depth (column)	L1	Minimum		
Aerosol columnar properties	L2	Minimum		
Aerosol profile microphysical and optical properties	L2	Minimum		

Annex 2. Schematics of the workflow for the ACTRIS aerosol remote sensing measurements

Annex 3. List of input parameters for the SCC operational configurations

The following table includes:

- Blue rows = Parameters which **have to be set by the PI** in the operational configuration. For some of them, check by CARS/ARES is performed before approving the configuration (based on QA tests or other documentation)
- Green rows = Parameters which **are fixed** in the operational configuration. For some of them, the PI can ask for justified changes. Approval of CARS/ARES is needed.
- White cells = Parameters which **are set by CARS** based on the QA tests

No.	Parameter	Description	Apply to	Value given by	Value	Source of info / Applicable test	Approval / check by
1	Emission wavelength	Wavelengths of all the transmitted laser beams	all the laser wavelengths	PI	Number	Datasheets (manufacturer)	CARS checks for plausibility
2	Detection wavelength	Wavelengths at which each lidar channel is detected (usually the interference filter center)	all channels	PI	Number	Datasheets (manufacturer)	CARS checks for plausibility
3	Detection bandwidth	Bandwidth used to detect each lidar channels (usually interference filter FWHM)	all channels	PI	Number	Datasheets (manufacturer)	CARS checks for plausibility
4	Range resolution	Raw signal range resolution	all channels	PI	Number	Datasheets (manufacturer)	CARS
5	Dead time	Dead time value corresponding to the whole PC acquisition system (PMT+discriminator+TR)	all PC channels	PI	Number	Datasheets (manufacturer) / Hardware test if possible	CARS
6	Trigger delay	Electronic delay (positive value) of the acquisition system with	all channels	PI	Number	Zero bin test	CARS

No.	Parameter	Description	Apply to	Value given by	Value	Source of info / Applicable test	Approval / check by
		respect to the laser pulse generation time					
7	First signal rangebin	Rangebin corresponding to signal backscattered at zero altitude above lidar system level	all channels	PI	Number	Zero bin test	CARS
8	Background subtraction mode	Method used for the atmospheric background calculation. Pre-trigger: average in signal pre-trigger region Far range: average in the signal far range region;	all channels	PI	Mandatory choice: Pre-trigger (if available)	-	CARS
10	Gluing options	Option combines the maximum count rate and the minimum analog signal level for the gluing range search. (see SCC documentation)	all PC/analog channels	PI	Default choice ¹ : PC signal: ID 17 analogue signal: ID 19	PI notifies if different from the default value	CARS
11	Polarization cross-talk parameters (G and H)	G and H parameters according to ²	all polarization sensitive channels	PI	Number	Optical calculation, possibly by manufacturer	CARS
12	Correction factor for	K parameter according to	all polarization sensitive channels	PI	Number	Optical calculation,	CARS

¹ the used default values with the IDs are for PC (ID 17): 10 MHz, and for analogue detection (ID 19) scale divisor: 5000

² Freudenthaler, V.: About the effects of polarising optics on lidar signals and the $\Delta 90$ calibration, Atmos. Meas. Tech., 9, 4181–4255, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-9-4181-2016>, 2016.

No.	Parameter	Description	Apply to	Value given by	Value	Source of info / Applicable test	Approval / check by
	polarization calibration (K)					possibly by manufacturer	
13	Handling of G, H, K parameters	Specify how G, H and K should be handled in case multiple values are available (average, take the closest in time to the measurements, take the latest....)	all polarization sensitive channels	PI	Mandatory choice: Take the closest in time before the measurement		ARES automatic check
	Polarisation calibration factor	Result from the polarisation calibration measurements.	all polarization sensitive channel pairs	PI	Number	ATLAS	CARS
14	Maximum statistical error below 2km	Maximum statistical error below 2km for each SCC products. Vertical resolution and time integration of each SCC product is fixed to meet this condition.	all SCC products	PI	Default choice: 50% Acceptable range: 10%-50%		ARES automatic check
15	Maximum statistical error above 2km	Maximum statistical error above 2km for each SCC products. Vertical resolution and time integration of each SCC product is fixed to meet this condition.	all SCC products	PI	Default choice: 50% Acceptable range: 20%-100%		ARES automatic check

No.	Parameter	Description	Apply to	Value given by	Value	Source of info / Applicable test	Approval / check by
16	Product detection limit	Detection limit of each SCC products at far range. Max. abs. statistical error of products.	all SCC products	PI	Default choice ³ : 5E-6 for extinction 1E-7 for backscatter		ARES automatic check
17	Minimum signal height	Minimum height to be used for the calculation of each SCC products. This value should be set to the full overlap height (if no overlap correction or signal ratio is applied)	all SCC signals	CARS	Number	Telecover	CARS
18	Maximum signal height	Maximum height to be used for the calculation of each SCC products. This value should be set to the height at which the lidar signal starts to be dominated by distortions, or at the uppermost height where strong aerosol layers (Cirrus or stratospheric layers can be measured in optimum conditions)	all SCC signals	CARS	Default choice: 20 km	Rayleigh fit incl. dark measurement	CARS

³ as suggested in the SCC interface

No.	Parameter	Description	Apply to	Value given by	Value	Source of info / Applicable test	Approval / check by
19	Preprocessing integration time	Time integration to consider in the pre-processing phase	all the low resolution SCC products	PI	Default choice: 30 min		ARES automatic check
20	Preprocessing vertical resolution	Vertical resolution at which interpolate pre-processed signal	all the low resolution SCC products	PI	Default choice: 15 m		ARES automatic check
21	Error calculation method	Method used to compute statistical error of each SCC product.	all SCC products	PI	Mandatory choice: Monte Carlo		ARES automatic check
22	Monte Carlo iterations	Number of iterations to consider for the statistical error estimation using Monte Carlo simulations	all the SCC products for which Monte Carlo simulations are used to compute statistical uncertainties	PI	Mandatory choice: 30	-	ARES automatic check
23	Extinction method	Method to use for the extinction retrieval	all extinction related SCC products	PI	Mandatory choice: Non-weighted linear fit	-	ARES automatic check
24	Particle Angstrom exponent	Value of particle Angstrom exponent to use in the extinction retrieval	all extinction related SCC products	PI	Number	Site characteristics (climatological values from the photometer measurements)	ARES
25	Elastic backscatter method	Method to use for the elastic backscatter retrieval	all Raman backscatter related SCC products	PI	Mandatory choice: Fernald-Klett	-	ARES automatic check

No.	Parameter	Description	Apply to	Value given by	Value	Source of info / Applicable test	Approval / check by
26	Fixed lidar ratio value	The fixed value of lidar ratio to use in the elastic backscatter retrieval.	all elastic backscatter related SCC products	PI	Number	Site characteristics (climatological values from past Raman measurements)	ARES
27	Error on lidar ratio value	The uncertainty on fixed value of lidar ratio to use in the elastic backscatter retrieval.	all elastic backscatter related SCC products	PI	Number	Site characteristics (climatological values from past Raman measurements)	ARES
29	Backscatter calibration options	Options to use for the calibration of Raman/elastic backscatter. These options specify the minimum and maximum heights, the width of the sliding window and the reference backscatter value to use in the Raman backscatter calibration.	all backscatter related SCC products	PI	Preferred choice: ID 36 ⁴ Alternative: ID 39 ⁵		ARES automatic check
30	Minimum Backscatter ratio for PLDR	Minimum backscatter ratio to consider in the calculation of particle linear depolarization ratio.	particle linear depolarization ratio SCC products	CARS	Default choice: 1.1	ATLAS	CARS

⁴ Reference height search: 2-20 km, window width: 500m, reference backscatter ratio: 1.0

⁵ Reference height search: 2-20 km, window width: 1000m, reference backscatter ratio: 1.0

Annex 4 Methodology for calculating data coverage for the lidar-related variables at stationary stations

The pre-defined schedule for the ACTRIS aerosol remote sensing National Observational Platforms, and for the EARLINET-ACTRIS associated lidar stations includes 5 observations per week, each with a duration of minimum 3 hours⁶, weather permitted ([Section 3.1 Measurement schedule for the ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms](#)):

Not all the variables can be measured in all timeslots. Raman channels can only be operated during night-time due to the low signal-to-noise ratio in daytime conditions. Therefore, the minimum number of expected measurements which can be used to calculate a certain variable with the above mandatory measurement schedule is variable-dependent, as follows:

Variable	Variable type	Constraint	No. of expected measurements
Attenuated backscatter profile	M	-	5 per week
Volume depolarization profile	M	-	5 per week
Particle backscatter coefficient profile	M	-	5 per week
Particle extinction coefficient profile	M	Night time	3 per week
Lidar ratio profile	M	Night time	3 per week
Ångström exponent profile	O	Night time	3 per week
Backscatter-related Ångström exponent profile	O	-	5 per week
Particle depolarization ratio profile	M	-	5 per week
Column integrated extinction	M	Night-time	3 per week

The above list is valid for each wavelength. The effective number of expected measurements take into account the minimum requirement for high power lidars: 1 wavelength equipped with both Raman and depolarization.

Note: Only raw data (input to SCC) are considered in the NF evaluation, as measure of the correct NF operation is terms of measurement performance, collection and submission to the DC.

The equation for calculating the data coverage (percentage) over the evaluation period for a variable X is:

$$\%Data\ coverage_{variableX} = \frac{No.ofcompliant\ measurements\ collected\ for\ variable\ X}{No.\ of\ expected\ measurements\ for\ variable\ X - No.\ of\ accepted\ exceptions'}$$

where:

- **No. of compliant measurements collected** is the number of datasets of at least one hour according to the schedule successfully submitted to the Single Calculus Chain and uploaded to the ACTRIS-EARLINET database
- **No. of expected measurements** is 5 or 3 (according to schedule, depending on the variable) multiplied by the number of weeks during the evaluation period
- **Accepted exceptions** are:

⁶ The 3 hours duration is necessary in order to identify at least 1 hour with clear sky (or at least without low clouds), so that the retrieval of the optical parameters is possible.

- Scheduled measurements not performed because the instrument is under repair, or on the way to / from being repaired
- Scheduled measurements not performed because of very low clouds, precipitation or fog (signal saturation)
- Scheduled measurements not performed because of force majeure (an extraordinary event or circumstance beyond the control of the facility, such as a war, strike, riot, crime, epidemic, or sudden legal change preventing the facility from fulfilling its obligations)

According to the [Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars](#), the aerosol remote sensing NFs are requested to maintain a log of the measurements not performed and reasons for not performing. This log is hosted by CARS and used by ARES to identify the accepted exceptions above.